

South Bellmore Veterinary Group Review: Simple steps to take care of your senior pets

Watching the growth of your pet is similar to a long worthwhile journey to your favorite place. You possibly took different turns but managed to arrive at your location with a smile on your face which can be akin to the feeling of seeing your pets grow into a dependable and strong animal. Taking care of a pet since its birth requires time and effort, but all of which is nothing compared to the loyalty your pet companion is giving to you.

However, once your pet reached its old age, it needs more love and care from you as its owner. Today, you can be confident with veterinary medicine because good developments were made in this field on the past years, which can help give longer and better lives to your pets. You need to implement changes on the lifestyle of your pets as well in accordance with their age.

In order for your pets to have a healthy aging, you need to take care and understand specific things such as the pet's genetics, diet, and environment. If the pet is 6-10 years old, or if your cat is 11-14 years old, then the pet belongs to the senior group already. But belonging to this group is not something you should be very scared about because, with the proper care and attention, your pets will surely live longer.

[South Bellmore Veterinary Group](#) wanted to help every pet owner in ensuring the good health of their senior pets through the following:

Regular Checkup

Schedule a regular checkup to your vet to monitor the condition of your pets. Even if your senior pet looks very healthy, you still need to take it to your vet at least twice a year. It is unavoidable to undergo some changes once an animal gets older where you can see effects regarding their age or worse, even witness them get some diseases easily. While it is somewhat normal to see senior pets having reduced vision and hearing, decrease in activity or increased sleeping, you can avoid them having major diseases if their illnesses were diagnosed early.

Even subtle changes on pets could mean some health problems, and with the help of the skills of a trusted vet, you can learn about the true condition of your pets since animals are good at hiding pain and diseases. Whether it is a big or small change happening on your pets, you should inform your vet right away.

Proper Diet

Animals need the right nutrition similar to humans, so give them a well-balanced diet. They won't stay healthy if you're not giving them nutritious foods. You can go with high-nutrient, easily-digested foods for older pets since they have a slower metabolism and they require a smaller amount of calories. You can contact or visit your vet to inquire about the best pet food

brands, ingredients or other formulas that can boost the health and medical condition of your pets.

Right Weight

Taking a proper and good amount of nutrition can result in a healthy weight. You must not tolerate overfeeding on your pets because experts said that this can increase the risk of cancer along with some diseases. Moreover, it can put a huge pressure on your pet's joints and even shorten its lifespan. Learn to properly monitor the weight of your pets along with the help of your vet.

Physical Activity

Being old doesn't mean that your pets don't have the ability to perform physical activities anymore. You can still count mild activities such as short walks, or a simple playtime as a good exercise for senior pets. A multitude of studies already prove the great role of physical activity to a healthy weight and heart, so don't miss such activities in taking care of your pets where it can also slow down joint degeneration. Don't make your older pets exert a great amount of energy, so when they seem tired, stop the activity right away. South Bellmore Veterinary Group wanted to highlight the importance of the mental health of your pets as well so don't forget to include mental exercise on their to-do list.

Oral Health

Older pets need attention on their dental hygiene as well. Make sure that your vet is doing professional cleaning to your loved pets so that they won't have gum disease, infection and other related diseases. In-home brushing is also advised between cleanings.

Safe and comfortable

These are two essential things that you should provide on your older pets. Put away objects that can be harmful on the path of your pets, and protect them whenever you leave home through baby gates. Organize their basic needs downstairs so that they won't have trouble climbing the stairs, especially if your pet has arthritis. Install stepstools or pet ramps to offer more convenience to your pets. Litter boxes should also be close to them and make their sleeping place soft with many blankets or put a heated pet bed.

Showing care and love

Humans and animals both need to feel love and care from the people around them. Show your pets you love them through a good belly rub or a gentle massage. Learn to properly groom your pets as well and make it as your bonding time with them. South Bellmore Veterinary Group also sees it effective to give them big hugs often and spend quality time together.